

Electrochemical Behaviour of Aldicarb

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The electrochemical reduction behaviour of aldicarb [2-methyl-2-(methylthio)propanaldehyde-*O*-(methylcarbamoyl)oxime] (1), an insecticide has been studied in the pH range 2–12 including 1 *M* HClO₄ and 1 *M* HCl in EtOH-water mixtures by employing d.c. polarography, cyclic voltammetry, a.c. polarography and differential pulse polarography. The number of electrons in the electrode process is determined by millicoulometry. The azomethine group is found to be reducible in 4 e^- process in solutions of pH \leq 4. The C=N–O linkage is observed to be reduced by a mechanism involving reductive fission of the N–O bond. Kinetic parameters such as diffusion coefficient and heterogeneous forward rate constants have been evaluated and reported.

One of the most important groups of pesticides is that of insecticides. In recent years effort has been made in developing new pesticides to achieve novel pesticides with interesting pesticidal activity. Aldicarb (1) is a broad spectrum soil applied systematic pesticide for the control of insects, mites and nematodes. In addition, it is a very effective nematicide usually affording seasonal control.

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N-Methyl carbamate pesticides are determined in vegetables and fruits by hplc¹. XAD-2 macroporous resin has been used for recovery of aldicarb and its metabolites in drinking water². A rapid two-step preconcentration procedure has been described for aldicarb determination in water by hplc using a 254-nm detector³. An inexpensive tlc procedure for estimation of carbamate insecticide residues in fruits and vegetables has been reported⁴. The residues of aldicarb and its metabolites have been determined in fruits, plants and soil⁵. But no attempt has been made to explain the reduction behaviour of the title

compound. The aim of the present study is to elucidate electrochemical reduction mechanism of aldicarb by using advanced electrochemical techniques (d.c. polarography, cyclic voltammetry, a.c. polarography) and to develop analytical procedure for the quantitative estimation by using differential pulse polarography.

Results and Discussion

Aldicarb is found to exhibit a single well defined cathodic wave/peak in solutions of pH \leq 4 which is seen to merge with hydrogen evolution in neutral and disappears completely in alkaline solutions. Typical voltammograms/polarograms are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The wave/peak obtained corresponds to a four-electron reduction of azomethine group to amino group (CH₂NH₂) by a mechanism involving reductive fission of the N–O bond in the C=N–O linkage.

The nature of the wave is found to be diffusion-controlled as shown by the linear dependence of limiting current on C , $h^{1/2}$, $v^{1/2}$. All these linear plots are observed to be passing through the origin indicating the absence of adsorption complications at the electrode surface. The irreversible nature of the electrode process is seen from the log-plot analysis. When E is plotted against $\log i/(i_d - i)$ the

Fig. 1. Typical differential pulse polarogramme of aldicarb in 1M HCl; concn. = 0.25 mM, drop time = 2 s, solvent = EtOH

value of the slope of the plot exceeds appreciably $59/n$ mV and the numerical value of $(E_{1/4}-E_{3/4})$ exceeds $56.4/n$ mV. This observation along with the absence of an anodic peak on the reverse scan in cyclic voltammetry confirmed the reduction process to be irreversible. Further, $E_{1/2}$, E_p , E_s and E_m are found to increase with concentration of the electroactive species to more negative values. This has been observed in the reduction of many organic compounds⁶ which is characteristic of the irreversible process.

An increase in the percentage of solvent ethanol in the polarographic test solution shifted the half-wave potentials towards more negative

values with simultaneous decrease in diffusion current. An increase in the solvent content resulted in a rise in pH⁷. The decrease in diffusion current may be partly due to an increase in the viscosity of the medium. This additional shift in $E_{1/2}$ may be attributed to a decrease in adsorbability and hence surface concentration of the depolariser with an increase in the percentage of nonaqueous solvent in the aqueous organic mixture⁸. A decrease in surface concentration would retard the electrode process resulting in a decrease in $E_{1/2}$ and i_d .

Fig. 2. Typical cyclic voltammogram of aldicarb in 1M HClO₄; concn. = 0.25 mM, scan rate = 40 mv s⁻¹, solvent = EtOH.

Millicoulometry is employed at pH 2 to find out the number of electrons involved in the electrode process. The results showed the number of electrons to be four. To identify the reduction product controlled potential electrolysis was carried out in 1M HCl at -0.905 V vs SCE, and the product was identified as amine by usual chemical tests⁹. The isolated amino product is confirmed by ir spectral (nujol) study (ν_{\max} 3 020, 1 620 cm^{-1}).

Kinetic data obtained with different techniques

are summarised in Tables 1-4. The diffusion coefficient values evaluated from all the techniques are in good agreement. This is evident particularly since no adsorption complications are involved in the electrode process. The heterogeneous forward rate constant values are found to decrease with increase in pH indicating that the electrode reaction tends to be more and more irreversible. The standard rate constants obtained in a.c. polarography are found to be high when compared to other techniques since the rate constants are evaluated at standard potentials in a.c. polarography.

TABLE 1-TYPICAL ELECTROCHEMICAL DATA OF D.C. POLAROGRAPHY

Concn. = 0.25 mM, drop time = 3 s					
Supporting electrolyte	$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d A	αn_a	$D \times 10^5$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$K_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹
1M HClO ₄	0.824	8.0	0.780	2.02	3.978×10^{-11}
1M HCl	0.840	7.3	0.765	1.68	3.17×10^{-11}
pH 2	0.974	6.8	0.750	1.46	1.083×10^{-12}
pH 4	1.050	6.2	0.740	1.22	3.427×10^{-13}

TABLE 2-TYPICAL ELECTROCHEMICAL DATA OF CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRY

Concn. = 0.25 mM, scan rate = 40 mV s ⁻¹					
Supporting electrolyte	$-E_p$ V	i_p A	αn_a	$D \times 10^5$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$K_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹
1M HClO ₄	0.82	7.8	0.76	1.98	5.81×10^{-11}
1M HCl	0.85	7.2	0.79	1.72	2.11×10^{-11}
pH 2	0.98	6.4	0.74	1.54	3.94×10^{-12}
pH 4	1.04	6.0	0.73	1.20	2.52×10^{-13}

TABLE 3-TYPICAL ELECTROCHEMICAL DATA OF A.C. POLAROGRAPHY

Concn. = 0.25 mM, drop time = 3 s					
Supporting electrolyte	$-E_s$ V	i_s A	α	$D \times 10^5$ cm ² s ⁻¹	K_s cm s ⁻¹
1M HClO ₄	0.86	3.5	0.32	1.05	7.73×10^{-7}
1M HCl	0.97	3.2	0.30	1.23	5.81×10^{-8}
pH 2	11.10	2.7	0.28	1.40	8.11×10^{-9}
pH 4	1.16	2.3	0.26	1.18	2.52×10^{-10}

Based on the results obtained the reduction mechanism, which corresponds to the reduction of the azomethine group, can be proposed for aldicarb (Scheme 1).

TABLE 4-TYPICAL ELECTROCHEMICAL DATA OF DIFFERENTIAL PULSE POLAROGRAPHY

Concn. = 0.25 mM, drop time = 2 s					
Supporting electrolyte	$-E_m$ V	i_m A	αn_a	$D \times 10^5$ cm ² s ⁻¹	$K_{f,h}^0$ cm s ⁻¹
1M HClO ₄	0.84	16.2	0.64	1.99	7.48×10^{-11}
1M HCl	0.86	14.5	0.67	1.80	4.79×10^{-11}
pH 2	1.01	13.0	0.66	1.60	3.98×10^{-12}
pH 4	1.10	12.1	0.64	1.25	9.95×10^{-14}

In acidic solution (pH \leq 4) :

Scheme 1

In the present investigation differential pulse polarography has been used for the quantitative estimation of aldicarb using calibration and standard addition methods. Polarographic peaks obtained in 1M HCl and 1M HClO₄ are well resolved and may be utilised for the analytical experiments. Linear calibration plots are obtained over the concentration range of 1.5×10^{-5} to 1.8×10^{-9} M in 1M HCl.

Experimental

A Princeton Applied Research Corporation (PARC) Model 364 polarographic analyser coupled with BD 8 Kipp and Zonen recorder was used for taking direct current polarograms. A three-electrode cell was employed containing a dropping mercury electrode (dme) of flow rate 2.73 mg s⁻¹ as working electrode, saturated calomel as the reference electrode and a platinum wire as the auxiliary electrode. A.C. polarography and differential pulse polarography were performed with a Metrohm E 506 polarecord connected

to a E 612 VA-scanner. The electrode assembly, in this case, consisted of a dropping mercury electrode (area 0.0223 cm^2) as the working electrode, saturated Ag/AgCl(s), Cl^- as the reference electrode and a platinum wire as the auxiliary electrode. A digital electronics 2000 X-Y/t recorder connected to Metrohm E 506 was used for recording the cyclic voltammograms. The hanging mercury drop electrode (area 0.2323 cm^2) was used as working electrode in cyclic voltammetry.

All experiments were performed at $25 \pm 1^\circ \text{ pH}$ measurements were carried out with a Elico digital pH meter. Dissolved air was removed from the solutions by degassing with oxygen-free nitrogen for 10 min.

The purity of aldicarb (West Germany) was tested by melting point determination. Other chemicals were of A.R. grade. Universal buffers ranging from pH 2 to 12 including 1 M HClO_4 and 1 M HCl were used as the supporting electrolytes.

The experimental solution (10–15 ml) was deoxygenated by passing oxygen-free nitrogen gas for 15 min. To ensure that the supporting electrolyte was sufficiently electroinactive, a blank run was taken.

Analytical procedure : The standard solution of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ was prepared by dissolving aldicarb in ethanol. An aliquot (1 ml) of the standard solution was transferred to the polarographic cell and made upto 10 ml with the supporting electrolyte to get the required concentration and then deoxygenated by bubbling nitrogen

gas for 10 min. After taking the polarograms, small increments of the standard solutions were added and then polarogram was recorded after each addition. The best precision was obtained in 1 M HCl with a drop time of 2 s, a pulse amplitude of 50 mV and an applied potential of $-0.85 \text{ V vs Ag/AgCl(s)/Cl}^-$. The relative standard deviation and correlation coefficients were found to be 1.99 and 0.991 respectively, for the replicants.

This aldicarb was also determined by liquid gas chromatographic method with lower detection limit of 1.0 to $0.2 \times 10^{-8} \text{ M}$. Due to the highly reproducible nature, easy handling and simple procedure, electrochemical method described here was preferred.

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